

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 63.2626 Max: 63.4108	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1263 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1162-1163	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION 1 square info block on top of floor 1173	Covered by SU: 1227	Fills SU:	Filled by SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX	
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input type="checkbox"/> Tiles	<input type="checkbox"/> Travertine	<input type="checkbox"/> Ash		
<input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae	<input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Dolia	<input type="checkbox"/> Basalt	<input type="checkbox"/> Human bones		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Clay	<input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mortar	<input type="checkbox"/> Sand	<input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth		
<input type="checkbox"/> Coins	<input type="checkbox"/> Silt	<input type="checkbox"/> Shells		
<input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		
<input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris	<input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)			
<input type="checkbox"/> Glass				
			Compaction	Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown
			<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White
			<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red
			<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow
				<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1227	Covers: 1173
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
block appeared during excavation of SU 1227

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: at western edge of Trench B 2010
Shape: cubic

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): —
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): —
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): —
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

The placement of this block seemed to be worth noting because of its position right on top of the tufo floor and next to the square poststand SU 1162. Whether or not it really had a function remains to be understood. Certain is, that the block is not part of a simple collapse of walls SU 1187 or SU 1245.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CHM	on	27.7.2010
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